

Editorial

Rise of the Machines

Artificial Intelligence (AI) refers to ‘the ability of a digital computer or a computer-controlled robot to perform tasks commonly associated with intelligent beings.’ It is a young field of research and scientific development. It concerns itself with the design and construction of machines with the ability to perform intelligent functions.

The field of artificial intelligence was, in a certain sense, inaugurated with the development of the digital computer in the 1940s. Alan Turing must be credited with developing a system that allowed a machine (computer) to solve a problem using an algorithm. His theory of computation has strongly influenced the field of computers and has laid the foundation for artificial intelligence. AI functions on the principle of basic computing: analysing data and generating an output that is beneficial and useful. All living beings also make use of this principle in mundane life albeit with varying degrees of complexity and consciousness.

AI tends to receive a negative portrayal in the media giving rise to the ‘Frankenstein Complex.’ But AI is not inherently bad or evil. It is a kind of technology that is capable of great good and can possibly catapult human beings to a higher quality of existence. AI is not mere science fiction; it is already present to us in small and large entities. The key question is: How are we really responding to it?

In this issue of *Vidyankur* you will find a variety of perspectives regarding Artificial Intelligence. Is it a boon or a bane? Does the

benefit outweigh the threat? The truth is that it is hard to predict because it is such a powerful technology. In the wrong hands it could be extremely hazardous. However, for the most part, it offers great promise for a brighter future and a better world.

I am grateful to the *Jnana Deepa Society for Science and Religion* for taking up such a relevant topic for discussion. They conducted an All-India Essay Contest and the best essays have been selected for publication in this issue. Kudos to all those who participated in the essay contest and shared their views. This is a topic that requires our attention. We have to grow in awareness so as to avoid falling victim to those who choose to use AI for nefarious purposes.

We live in an age where AI is growing in capacity and application. It is being fed huge amounts of data thanks to our excessive use of the internet. For the most part, AI helps make our digital life so much easier by recommending stuff we might enjoy and helping us complete our search faster. But it also studies us — our habits, our likes and dislikes, our searches; it endeavours to collect our personal data in the name of improving our online experience but has the possibility of manipulating us and in worst case scenarios, holding us to ransom. We should not give in to the Frankenstein Complex and become mechanized by it rather we ought to maintain control at all times.

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